

Beneficial Yet Not Enough: Chinese Students' Coping Strategies and Perceptions toward Peer Interaction and Feedback

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ABSTRACT

This study examines Chinese university students' coping strategies and perceptions of peer corrective feedback (PCF) during peer interaction (PI) activities. Data were collected from 24 English as a second language (ESL) students at an Australian university through three group activities and semi-structured interviews and were analysed qualitatively. The findings showed that participants consciously or unconsciously navigate dual roles, shifting between feedback receivers and providers. They also expressed favourable attitudes towards PCF but observed varying perceptions toward PI. Further, politeness strategies, due to Chinese cultural influences, were prevalent among students to maintain interpersonal harmony. These findings offer valuable insights into classroom interactions and the implementation of PCF. Teachers are encouraged to consider students' cultural orientations concerning PI and PCF, carefully group students from diverse backgrounds, and employ strategies that enhance PI and PCF without creating awkwardness while maintaining classroom harmony.

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INTRODUCTION

Peer interaction, defined as "any communicative activity carried out between learners with minimal or no teacher involvement" (Philp et al., 2014, p. 3), fosters students' engagement in classroom activities. Similar to teacher-student interactions, peer interaction plays a significant role in second language (L2) learning activities (Sato & Ballinger, 2016).

Over the past few decades, extensive research has highlighted the critical role of conversation in second language (L2) learning, emphasising its importance as a context for language acquisition (e.g., Long, 2007; Mackey, 2012). While much of this research has traditionally focused on learner-teacher and learner-native speaker interactions, there is growing interest in peer interaction (PI), its unique characteristics, and the benefits it offers for L2 development (Sato & Ballinger, 2016).

Despite its advantages, PI is often perceived as less effective in fostering linguistic accuracy compared to teacher-learner or learner-native speaker interactions, primarily due to the less frequent provision of corrective feedback (e.g., Fujii & Mackey, 2009; Philp et al., 2010; Sippel, 2020). To address this limitation, some scholars advocate for training learners to provide corrective feedback to each other during PI (e.g., Martin & Sippel, 2021; Sato & Lyster, 2012).

Additionally, numerous studies have examined learners' attitudes and perceptions of PI and corrective feedback (e.g., Ha & Nguyen, 2021; Jiang & Ironsi, 2024; Sippel, 2020; Schulz, 1996; Yoshida, 2008), offering valuable insights into how learners engage in feedback practices during peer interactions. These studies also explore the influence of learner backgrounds—such as proficiency level, first language (L1), and gender—on PI and peer corrective feedback (PCF), particularly about group and pair composition (e.g., Choi & Iwashita, 2016; Gass & Veronis, 1986; Zabini & Ghahramanzadeh, 2022).

Research on intercultural communication further indicates that learners often transfer their L1 communication styles to L2 interactions (e.g., Fitzgerald, 2003). Similarly, cross-cultural collaborative writing studies have examined how students from different cultural backgrounds navigate joint writing tasks and how cultural

norms influence their interactions and contributions (Chang et al., 2024; Van Rompay-Bartels & Geessink, 2023). However, it remains unclear how factors, such as L1 communication styles and prior learning experiences, shape learners' approaches to PI and PCF.

To address this gap, the present study investigates how L1 Chinese university students in Australia employ strategies and provide feedback during peer interaction activities and how their perceptions influence their performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Peer corrective feedback (PCF) in L2 learning involves learners receiving corrective input from fellow students during interactions. Unlike teacher or expert feedback, peer feedback comes from learners of equal status, offering both advantages and limitations. While this equitable relationship can create a more comfortable communication environment, it often results in less frequent and lower quality feedback than that provided by teachers or native speakers (Pica et al., 1996; Davin & Donato, 2013).

Early peer interaction and feedback research were primarily grounded in cognitive interactionist perspectives, particularly Long's Interaction Hypothesis (Long, 1996, 2007). However, recent studies have increasingly drawn on sociocultural theory to understand better peer feedback dynamics (e.g., Kos, 2022; Pohner & Leontjev, 2022; Xi & Lantolf, 2020). Research has shown that peer feedback occurs less frequently and with varying effectiveness (Adams, 2007; Lambert et al., 2017; Toth, 2008). One contributing factor is that learners often struggle to give and interpret peer feedback due to limited confidence in their own and their peers' linguistic abilities (Baharudin & Razali, 2021). Additionally, scepticism regarding peer feedback—particularly doubts about its accuracy—can make learners hesitant to rely on their peers' corrections (Yoshida, 2008; Jiang & Ironsi, 2022; Katayama, 2007).

However, learners' attitudes toward peer feedback can shift in environments where they interact with more proficient peers. In such contexts, they may recognise the value of peer feedback (Sato & Lyster, 2012). Furthermore, learners generally find peer interactions more engaging than teacher feedback, and positive past experiences with proficient peers can enhance their willingness to accept peer feedback (Philp & Mackey, 2010). Studies suggest that raising awareness and

training in peer feedback strategies can significantly improve effectiveness (e.g., Fujii et al., 2016; Martin & Sippel, 2021; Sato, 2010; Sippel, 2020).

Beyond learner attitudes, cultural factors significantly shape peer interaction and feedback dynamics. Face-saving concerns, collectivist values, and the desire to maintain social harmony influence how feedback is given and received. Zhu and Bresnahan's (2006) study on collective face—the need to uphold an ingroup's public image—found that Chinese international students exhibited stronger collective face concerns than their American counterparts when responding to an ingroup member's failure. In feedback settings, this cultural orientation may discourage direct criticism and hinder peer feedback exchanges (Hyland, 2000).

For example, Chinese students often feel uncomfortable critiquing their peers' work, as teacher-centred education systems in East Asia emphasise authority and discourage open critique among students (Hyland & Hyland, 2001; Zhao, 2011). Learners from such backgrounds may struggle to adopt unfamiliar interactive learning styles, leading to hesitation and uncertainty when providing feedback.

Furthermore, research on cross-cultural collaboration in writing highlights additional complexities arising from cultural differences (e.g., Allaei & Connor, 1990; Albeshier, 2024; Chang et al., 2024; Van Rompay-Bartels & Geessink, 2023). For instance, Van Rompay-Bartels and Geessink (2023) found that students from individualistic cultures tend to emphasise personal contributions, whereas those from collectivist cultures prioritise group harmony. These cultural differences can result in misunderstandings and conflicts during group work. Additionally, students may hesitate to provide direct criticism or assert their opinions due to cultural norms that value deference and face-saving.

In summary, while peer interaction and peer feedback hold significant potential for L2 development, their effectiveness is shaped by learners' attitudes, cultural influences, and task design. Addressing these factors can help maximise the benefits of peer interaction (PI) and corrective feedback (PCF) in language learning. The current study seeks to answer the following question: “What are Chinese ESL learners’ strategies and perceptions of peer interaction and corrective feedback?”

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a qualitative approach to examine students' strategies for engaging in peer interactions (PI) and providing peer corrective feedback (PCF) in ESL contexts. Given the complexity and individual nature of beliefs and perceptions (Basturkmen, 2012), a qualitative approach was well-suited for gaining nuanced insights into students' perceived effectiveness of PI and PCF.

Participants

Twenty-four Chinese international students from various study majors from Australian universities participated (aged 18 to 30; 5 males and 19 females). Their proficiency ranged from B2 to C1, which are converted to CEFR equivalents from their recent standardised English Proficiency test scores ($N = 4$ for B1, 15 for B2 and 5 for C1)

Instruments and Data Collection Procedure

This study assessed learners' perceptions of PI after participating in a researcher-designed PCF session. Participants were informed about the study, completed a demographic questionnaire, and signed a consent form. They then engaged in a group writing task based on opinion-gap discussions (Choi & Iwashita, 2016; Spinelli, 2024), designed to foster interaction and enhance motivation (Dörnyei, 1994). Adapted from Sipple (2020), interview questions explored learners' feelings and beliefs about PI and PCF. Data was collected over three days with 24 participants (eight participants per day). Each day, a group of eight participants carried out three activities and participated in a semi-structured interview after the initial briefing and warm-up activity.

Group Discussion (Step 1) and Collaborative Writing (Step 2) Tasks

Participants completed two tasks: group discussions to share opinions and collaborative writing in pairs. The group was then divided into pairs, each participating in collaborative writing separately before regrouping for the next step. These tasks were adapted from previous studies (Spinelli, 2024).

Peer Corrective Feedback (PCF) Task (Steps 3 and 4)

Participants exchanged writing and watched a training video on how to provide feedback before giving corrective feedback, which was followed by two peer

feedback sessions without the writer (Step 3) and in the presence of the writer (Step 4). The training video provided practical experience in understanding the procedure of commenting on others' work.

Focus Group Interview (Step 5)

A focus group interview followed, designed to elicit deeper insights into participants' beliefs about peer interaction and feedback. As mentioned above, interview questions, adapted from Sipple (2020), covered perceptions of peer interaction and corrective feedback. Both English and Mandarin were used to facilitate comfort and clarity.

Data Analysis and Coding

The recorded sessions, primarily in Mandarin, were transcribed using voice recognition software with manual editing due to frequent code-mixing. To ensure accuracy, transcripts were manually translated into English, reviewed, and verified by native Mandarin speakers. Interaction data were coded in terms of corrective feedback episodes. Interview transcripts were re-evaluated, and participant identities were anonymised. Perceptions of peer interactions and corrective feedback were analysed through participants' actual behaviour during group tasks, offering more profound insights into their feedback practices.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

This study examines the interaction strategies employed by L1 Chinese ESL students in an L2 communication environment and their perceptions of peer interaction (PI) and peer corrective feedback (PCF). To address the research question, the study analysed both the communication strategies used by Chinese ESL students and their perceptions of PI and PCF, drawing on data from three task sessions and post-task interviews.

Interaction Strategies

The findings show that many students resort to strategies to maintain harmony during PI and PCI sessions regardless of whether they are required to provide feedback.

As explained in the methodology section, the group discussion task (Step 1) provided a scenario in which student participants played the role of a presentation team. All participants in six groups seemed to perform similarly, as shown in the two excerpts from three different groups below.

Excerpt 1

48 P7 (04:12): Um, so let me share my thoughts first. I'm more inclined towards the last option, Wang. It's because, you know, from my personal perspective, I prefer someone who's good at thinking.....

53 P6(06:04): Ah, well, I'm leaning towards the middle one. I feel like, maybe it's because I haven't had much experience with that kind of group presentation thing, but I think slides could be pretty crucial in the speech.....

Excerpt 2

50 P14: Well, I might go for the third one as well [RA3: Yeah]. Considering my own situation, my English proficiency is a bit lower [RA3: Yeah]...

58 P13: Yum, yeah, so, if I bring it into my field, he might have a lot of suggestions, like what instrument to use or the arrangement direction...

Group discussion task does not require participants to comment on others' views during the discussion, so the strategies that the participants employed to reach an agreement to choose one student were mainly to share their thoughts and views without insisting on their own preferred person forward, as shown in the use of phrases such as "from my perspective", "considering my situation", or "if I bring this into my field". For example, in Excerpt 1, where Participants 7 and 6 had different opinions on the member selections, Participant 6 neither agreed with nor rejected Participant 7's view as Participant 7 restrained the context by politely saying, "From my perspective...". As a result, Participant 6 continued to express his view by pointing to the relevant experience of not having many experiences in peer interactions. Therefore, it can be noticed that when conducting a peer interaction activity where there is no need for critiques or corrective feedback, participants still tend to apply the interactional strategies more conservatively by emphasising the subjectivity and specifically addressing contexts of the answers to avoid any potential conflicts or arguments with or without any disagreements.

In PCI activities (Steps 3 and 4), most student participants tended to use more cautious language in the presence of the feedback receivers (Step 4), regardless of how they expressed their opinions or provided peer corrective feedback before (Step 3) as shown in the example below (Excerpt 3).

Excerpt 3

(Step 3)

429 P5(18:14):Add "to" here.

430 P6:Huh?

431 P5:It needs to add "to" in the middle here

432 P6:Want to you((Writing))Nah. Is it there yet?

433 P5: Is she repeating this?

.....

(Step 4)

492 RA3: Is there anything else you feel needs to be revised?

493 P5: Nothing else, but I think the word "everything" could be replaced with "all," it would sound more conversational. Everything sounds a bit awkward, and other than that, I think it's pretty, and perfect.

In Excerpt 3, Participants 5 and 6 provided comments on the imperative sentences and direct questioning or negations but used subjective markers ("*I think*"), modal verbs ("*could*", "*would*") and affirmations ("*pretty*", "*perfect*") to soften their tones. Regardless of how direct and critical they performed during the peer corrective feedback process without the feedback receiver (Step 3), they all tended to apply politeness strategies within the presence of the author of the text (Step 4) to avoid any potential conflicts or arguments.

These applications of politeness strategies employed throughout activities (Step 1-4) align with Zhu and Bresnahan's (2018) findings on collective face dynamics between American domestic students and Chinese international students. Their study revealed that Chinese international students exhibited a greater sensitivity

to face-threatening scenarios and a higher tendency to employ avoidance strategies to mitigate potential face-threatening events within the group (Zhu & Bresnahan, 2018). Further, the findings align with studies on the Chinese stereotypical culture conducted before the emergence of the postmodernism paradigm (Allaei & Connor, 1990; Carson & Nelson, 1996). Specifically, Carson and Nelson's study revealed the mismatch in perceptions and behaviours of Chinese ESL students in their writing groups, where they would opt for pleasing their peers socially instead of exhibiting any negative criticising comments that could threaten their peers' faces. Similar to their results, participants in this study also tended to apply politeness strategies during PI and PCF.

Perceptions

Findings regarding student participants' perceptions of PI and PCF suggested that most participants held a cautious and neutral perception of PI and preferred a combination of teacher feedback and PCF.

Excerpt 4

572 13:It's better together((laugh))

573 15:Well, yeah, it's okay because sometimes the teacher's views aren't entirely comprehensive, and classmates might approach things from the latest events, making it easier to understand.

In the post-task interview, most participants preferred receiving corrective feedback from multiple sources—both peers and teachers—rather than relying solely on their own judgment. A systematic literature review on peer interactions and feedback among students (Baharudin & Razali, 2021) highlights the positive impact of peer interactions on improving ESL and EFL students' writing performance (Huisman et al., 2018; Fathi & Khodabakhsh, 2019).

However, despite these positive findings, Baharudin and Razali (2021) also cited studies suggesting that teacher feedback carried greater influence than peer feedback in Asian EFL contexts (Miao et al., 2006; Ruegg, 2018). This preference for teacher feedback may stem from the traditionally authoritative and hierarchical role of teachers in Asian cultures (Baharudin & Razali, 2021). In contrast, the present study offers an alternative perspective: rather than favouring either peer or teacher feedback exclusively, participants preferred a combination of both. This preference may be attributed to the fact that the participants in the

current study have spent a significant amount of time in Australia and have become accustomed to providing feedback proactively without feeling inhibited or perceiving it as impolite.

Apart from cultural background as a potential factor, an interesting trend emerged when peer corrective feedback (PCF) was mentioned during the interviews. Overall, students viewed PCF as a potentially useful resource when accompanied by teacher feedback, despite their scepticism regarding its reliability due to peers' varying proficiency levels. Additionally, all participants acknowledged the importance of incorporating PCF in ESL classrooms, aligning with the findings of Sato's (2013) study.

IMPLICATIONS

The findings showed that cultural differences are considered one of the primary factors that can impact students' strategies to employ PCF in PI and perceptions of PI and PCF during interactional activities. As Van Rompay-Bartels and Geessink (2023) emphasised, different cultural comprehensions on peer feedback directly impact international students' interactions with other peers in the classroom. Additionally, this study addresses the potential issues of cultural gaps in interactional activities in the classroom. In addition to cultural factors, this study also provides an alternative view on improving peer interaction and corrective feedback effectiveness. When student participants discussed peer interaction and peer corrective feedback in different contexts, they drew examples from their past experiences.

For effective classroom practice, teachers should consider students' cultural orientations when facilitating peer interaction and corrective feedback. Thoughtfully grouping students from diverse backgrounds can help foster a more inclusive and supportive learning environment. Moreover, implementing strategies that promote meaningful engagement while minimising discomfort is essential for maintaining classroom harmony.

Educators can provide structured training on giving and receiving feedback to help students navigate cultural differences in feedback practices. Such training should build confidence, reduce anxiety, and encourage constructive communication. Techniques like modelling effective feedback, using structured peer review guidelines, and incorporating anonymous or indirect feedback can help students

feel more at ease. Teachers can cultivate a more supportive and productive peer feedback culture by equipping learners with these skills.

CONCLUSION

This study examines how L1 Chinese ESL learners navigate peer interactions, highlighting their use of various interaction strategies and feedback approaches following brief training. The data reveal that participants were generally hesitant to provide direct feedback, instead relying on politeness strategies to maintain social harmony. These findings emphasise the importance of incorporating training in peer interaction (PI) and peer corrective feedback (PCF) at the outset of tertiary programs. Such training can enhance engagement and foster a more inclusive academic community for international and local students. Acknowledging learners' cultural backgrounds is crucial in encouraging active participation and promoting constructive feedback exchanges.

While this study provides valuable insights into learner strategies and perceptions of PI and PCF and its pedagogical implications, its small sample size and focus on Chinese students with relatively lower English proficiency may limit its generalisability. Other factors influencing perceptions of peer interaction (PI) and peer corrective feedback (PCF), such as prior learning experiences and educational backgrounds, remain underexplored. Although participants were provided with a training video, their understanding of PI and PCF remained limited, indicating the need for more comprehensive and interactive instructional approaches in future research.

Despite its small scale, this study highlights how cultural backgrounds shape learners' communication strategies and perceptions of PI and PCF, ultimately influencing their interactions in ESL contexts. To build on these findings, future research should incorporate more extensive and diverse participant groups to understand better how cultural differences affect peer interactions. Additionally, exploring more effective training methods, such as hands-on workshops or guided peer feedback sessions, could provide deeper insights into enhancing communication and feedback practices in multicultural learning environments.

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